

Extended Solution to the St. Petersburg Problem

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Abstract: This essay extends Arlet and others' solution to the St. Petersburg problem, but explicitly allows for the possibility of an infinite bankroll. The maximum bet remains finite (in units of present-day dollars) and Bayesian decision theory proves to be off the hook of this and related infinite-reward "paradoxes".

Section One: A Liberal Review of Arlet's Solution

How much should you be willing to pay to play the following game? If you play, you automatically win at least a dollar. Take a penny. Flip it. If it comes up heads, flip it again. Repeat until it comes up tails. Here's what I'm offering: the pot starts at a dollar. Every time you get to flip the penny, I'll double the pot. So if you flip it five times and the fifth flip is tails, you automatically double it with the first flip to \$2, then it's 4, 8, 16, \$32. Thirty-two bucks. Take it home.

So: what do you pay, to play the game once?

Let's calculate the upper limit of what a good gambler would pay: If we play this game an infinite number of times, what do we get on the average game? We should generally be willing to bet no more than that amount.

It turns out that the gambler's bet appears to be infinite; we can expect, on average, infinite winnings! Arlet, and who-knows-how-many others, solved the paradox as I have by saying, in essence, "Show me da money!" I'll give a complete rendition of the same argument, but follow it through to indeed allow the gamble to grow without bounds. We shall discover the "infinite" sum to converge nonetheless; the bet tops off at around forty-four present-day U.S. dollars, and then *diminishes to nothing*. This result accounts for the minimal inflationary effects of increasing the global quantity of currency. However, let's start simple.

You ought to say, "show me the money," because the bet is not really infinite. If you keep on getting heads, my money will eventually run out. And so how much am I *really* putting on the table? A million? A billion?

There aren't much more than six trillion, mostly electronic (and multiply-counted) greenbacks in the world. Then you have non-U.S. currency for which we have poor statistics, or they are in proprietary languages. For convenience, I shall assume that the global money supply is \$8.8 trillion (\$2⁴³), which is close enough for the present discussion.

I don't want to start with \$8.8 trillion, but we'll get there and beyond. For now let's say I'm putting \$1,024 on the table. Ten tosses (requiring nine consecutive heads), and I'm bankrupt. Since I'm admitting this right from the start, we can calculate the clever gambler's maximum bet straightforwardly, without any infinite results.

Let's play 1,024 games with a payout of up to \$1,024. I am actually doing the statistics as if we are playing a very large number of games, G , dividing the number of wins at each flip-level (the total number of coin tosses in a game) by the very same G , and multiplying the result by 1,024. This gives us a handy number of games, but the perfect statistics that any honest casino would envy.

Here's a table enumerating the results of all 1,024 games.

Flips per game	Payout per game (\$)	Expected wins in 1,024 games	Total Payout (\$)
1	2	512	1,024
2	4	256	1,024
3	8	128	1,024
4	16	64	1,024
5	32	32	1,024
6	64	16	1,024
7	128	8	1,024
8	256	4	1,024
9	512	2	1,024
10+	1,024	2	2,048
TOTALS:		1,024 games	\$11,264

Let's check my math in the table. You always get to flip the coin once - that's your first turn. Half the time it'll come up heads, so you'll get to flip it again. Therefore, you can expect to get *just one flip* half the time, and two or more flips the other half. Adding up the projected wins from the two-flip level to the 10+ end-state, we get 512, the same as the number of wins projected for the one-flip

game. So the first coin toss ends half the games. Well that makes sense.

Your second toss also comes out heads half the time. Therefore, the number of games wherein you get *just two flips* should equal the number of games wherein you get three flips or more. This is borne out: the number of games that allow from 3 to 10+ flips totals 256, the same as the number of games we have slated for a two-flip finish.

The same logic holds through the nine-flip game, which proves that we've properly distributed the number of projected wins to that point. And on the ninth flip, there is a 50/50 chance that it'll come up heads. And if it's heads, we have a 10+ -flip game, but if it falls tails we have a nine-flip game. (It doesn't matter how the 10th flip comes out, because I've only got \$1,024, sorry to say). Therefore the odds are perfectly even for a nine- or ten-flip finish: it rests on a single coin toss, your ninth. And if we check the table, indeed, I claimed that we should expect the same number of wins for both the ultimate and the penultimate end-state: two.

Now let us return to that million-dollar question: how much should you pay to play, at most? In other words (according to Bayesian decision theory) what are the average winnings per game?

Let's see. Summed over all 1,024 games, we win the same total amount at every flip-level, \$1,024 - except at the 10+ end-state, which brings in \$2,048. (Here, I'm just multiplying the payout per game by the number of wins at that level). Therefore the grand total is $(9 * \$1,024) + \$2,048$: \$11,264. And don't forget we won this \$11,264 in a total of 1,024 games. The average winnings per game amounts to $\$11,264/1,024 = \11.00 .

Therefore, if \$1,024 is all the money I'm laying down, then the maximum amount you are willing to pay to play is \$11.00, unless you're a sucker. That's not an intuitively shocking figure if you ask me, but we aren't through yet. We have to see what happens as we increase the maximum payout to infinity.

One step at a time. Let's add one row to the table, doubling the maximum payout to \$2,048, at 11+ flips. And

now, merely for ease of analysis, let's play twice as many games: 2,048:

Flips per game	Payout per game (\$)	Expected wins in 2,048 games	Total Payout (\$)
1	2	1,024	2,048
2	4	512	2,048
3	8	256	2,048
4	16	128	2,048
5	32	64	2,048
6	64	32	2,048
7	128	16	2,048
8	256	8	2,048
9	512	4	2,048
10	1,024	2	2,048
11+	2,048	2	4,096
TOTALS:		2,048 games	\$24,576

With the maximum pot doubled, we get a total payout of $\$2,048 \times 10 + \$4,096 = \$24,576$ in 2,048 games, yielding an average of $\$24,576 / 2,048 = \12 per game. So if \$2,048 is the maximum amount of your winnings, then you should bet \$12.00 at the very most.

Again, this does not seem like a particularly unreasonable figure to pay for such a game. The problem is that the amount we can expect to win on average increases *without bounds*, as we up the amount on the table. Should the gambler bet boundlessly higher and higher? By Zeus! Is that true??!

First we have to nail down the pattern. Let's see.. Every time we double the maximum payout, we add one possible, meaningful flip per game. In other words, we add a row to our table. Let's also double the total number of games that we play - it's convenient, and we divide them out at the end, anyway. Go on, do the math: what are the average winnings, given the maximum payout?

For the n -flip game, the maximum payout will be $\$2^n$, and we'll play 2^n games. You can easily see that the *total* payout will be $\$2^n * (n + 1)$, if we play 2^n games (with perfect statistics).

The average payout, then, will be:

$$\{\$2^n * (n + 1)\} / 2^n = n + 1 \text{ dollars.}$$

So that's what we bet, given a bankroll of $2^n \dots (n + 1)$ dollars. Parenthetically, if you want to calculate n from the maximum bet B , $n = \log_2(B)$.

Let's try out the new formulas. For 10 maximum flips, we get:

Max Flips (n): 10
Max payout: $\$2^{10} = 1,024$
Avg. Payout: $10 + 1 = \$11.00$

Lo and behold. For 11 flips:

Max payout: $\$2^{11} = 2,048$
Avg. Payout: $11 + 1 = \$12.00$

It does seem to work. Now, let me remind you of the supposed paradox: as the maximum payout increases, the average payout increases without bounds. Is it true?

Every time I add one to n , I'm doubling the amount of money that's on the table. As the maximum payout increases indefinitely, n increases indefinitely. And every time I increase n by one, the formula, which says how much I'm willing to pay to play the game, spits out an extra dollar,

Yes, then, of course. If I double the amount of money on the table an infinite number of times, it will add a dollar to that reasonable amount an infinite number of times as well. That's where the paradox comes in. Evidently, we should bet an infinite amount.

Here's where the paradox dissolves. All the money in the world comes to something like 2^{43} dollars. Around 8.8 trillion US dollars. Now, if practically all the money in the world is on the table, and it's 8.8 trillion dollars, the gambler should bet no more than $(43+1) = 44$ dollars.

Section Two: Onward to Infinity

Up to this point, the same argument has been made by Arlet and others. Robert Martin (2001) notes:

Other facts make an upper limit L plausible, such as the limit on the amount of money available in the world. Perhaps all these financial limits can be overridden if we conceive

of the game's being offered by a state capable of printing all the money it wanted to. This state could pay any prize whatever; but printing up and handing out a huge amount of cash would create havoc with any economy, so no rational state would. (Martin)

But why not follow it through? Suppose the bank is not you or I, but someone considerably more powerful; someone who could double the amount of currency in the world in order to back a doubled wager.

Mind you, I'm with Martin: an economic catastrophe would ensue if someone (presumably the world's governments) doubled the amount of money in the world. The backlash would likely devalue the currency out of proportion to the increase. But let's assume that the world's money supply is doubled so smoothly that neither labor nor production grinds to a halt, and all the same commodities can still be bought.

In that overly generous case, the value of a post-doubling dollar in terms of labor, land and merchandise, is half that of a pre-doubling dollar.

Our earlier calculation remains unchanged: you can reasonably bet an additional dollar per unit increase of n , whatever that dollar is worth. But its value is diminished, in comparison to pre-doubling dollars...

After $n = 43$ has come and gone, the money supply has to be doubled every time we double the maximum winnings in the game. The number of times the supply is doubled is therefore $n - 43$. And every time we double the money supply, the value of a dollar gets halved. Therefore, after n surpasses 43, *and stating our gamble in pre-doubling dollars*, the amount we are willing to pay is:

$$(n + 1) / 2^{n-43}$$

This is not a summation, mind you, but the total value of what you should pay to play, restated in pre-doubling dollars. As n approaches infinity, the denominator rapidly outpaces the numerator, and the value of your wager diminishes to ZILCH.

This is in accordance with intuition, because you would have to toss and get heads an infinite number of times to justify your outlay of *any* finite chunk of pre-doubling change. All pre-doubling currency has been doubled *ad*

infinitum, whereas the game still pays out finite sums of money for a finite number of tosses.

In conclusion, if you are offered the St. Petersburg game, demand that the payer *show you the money*. If they have something approximating all the money in the world, you can pay \$44 to play, give or take a couple dollars. But as a powerful bank increases the global money supply *ad infinitum*, the total value of your bet plummets to zero—even as you continue to increase your wager by a dollar per doubling. Stick with the equation — pay $\$(n + 1)$ or less — and you will never pay more than forty-four present-day dollars.

Postscript

Bayesian decision theory does not have to be restricted in order to account for the St. Petersburg Paradox. It is already forbidden to compare 1976 dollars and 2003 dollars evenly; they are not the same units. No more so are the “dollars” in the paradox comparable, before and after the global money-supply is doubled. And yet, when the end-states are adjusted to equivalent units there is no paradox.

A similar analysis answers the Infinite Money Machine problem as well:

Imagine you were offered the following deal. For a price to be negotiated, you will be given permanent possession of a cash machine with the following unusual property: every time you punch in a dollar amount, that amount is extruded. This is not a withdrawal from your account; neither will you later be billed for it. You can do this as often as you care to. Now, how much would you offer to pay for this machine? (Martin)

The infinite cash-machine is subject to inflationary complications as well. As you increase the money supply by using this machine, you decrease the value of money. If you use the thing slowly enough that you do not wreck economic production, or the political stability that your dollars rely upon, then the value of “the total amount of money in the world” remains constant, in terms of goods and services on the market.

We may conclude that the machine is worth a finite amount of present-day dollars: not over 8.8 trillion. In other words, the maximum possible dollar-value of this machine is “all the money in the world,” stated in present-day dollars.

An Aside for Clever Readers

Since its introduction by the legendary Daniel Bernoulli, the St. Petersburg Paradox has been associated with the law of diminishing marginal utility. Unfortunately, that handy rule of thumb is a wholly unwarranted consideration in this particular betting problem. Inflationary factors eclipse its importance.

Moreover, the law of diminishing marginal utility, and indeed all reasonable considerations of utility in gambling problems, are limited in a fashion that is rarely accounted for: if the marginal utility of acquisition of a given amount of money is nearly zero coming in, then the *loss* of the same is nearly zero as well (after acquisition). This consideration reduces the relevance upon a given decision of smooth, non-linear relationships between dollar-values and utilities.

Concluding Generalization

In any ordinary Bayesian problem having dollar-values as the end-states, one may freely convert the dollar-values to percentages of the global money supply. However, in order to compare like units, we are *required* to perform such a conversion if the value of a dollar changes over the course of the problem. Furthermore, if the total *value* of the global money supply changes (as in the event of a major economic disruption), one should perform further conversions. The quantification of these subsequent conversions belongs to the field of macroeconomics, not decision theory.

These procedures do not constitute any change to classical decision theory, wherein it is already mandatory that we compare like units.

Works Cited

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